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Does reservation alter the mind sets? A research enquiry vis-à-vis fear of failure, locus of control and personal effectiveness among undergraduate girl students across disciplines

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In times when equality and social justice is being talked about in all spheres of life, this research is an attempt made to compare psychological states of mind of undergraduate girl-students enrolled in different disciplines coming from reserved and general categories. The study was carried out on 80 reserved and 80 general category students from four different disciplines-Social Science, Literature, Commerce and Computer Science of an under graduate college for women. The relationships among Personal effectiveness, Locus of Control, and Fear of Failure varied with respect to the targeted groups. Fear of Failure and Openness to Feedback (a sub-category of Personal effectiveness) could evoke difference among the various disciplines. In the case of categories, differences were obtained for internal locus of control and external (luck) locus of control only. Whereas when the disciplines and categories were taken together, only fear of failure could bring forward the significant difference.

Keywords: General Category, Reserved Category, Educational Disciplines, Locus of Control, Personal Effectiveness, Fear of Failure

INTRODUCTION

India has a polygenetic population and is an amalgamation of myriad races and cultures. The multilingual, multicultural and multiracial society is spread all over the Indian subcontinent which forms the basis of communal diversification. With the existence of social equity and justice, there exists a desire amongst the people to form their own collective identity resulting in formation of social groups and creation of a unique Indian caste based society structure. According to social thinkers, socialization is the means by which social and cultural continuity is attained in a society. From the very moment an individual is born he/she is being socialized into the caste, religion and gender based societal role. Thus not only the family environment but also the society and the culture in which the children are brought up become very important.

Even though the constitution of India fosters Right to Equality as one of the Fundamental Rights, the irony is that signs of discontent are evident due to the vast disparity in terms of resources both physical and psychological among various sections of the country. This results in emergence of certain groups such as the Reserved (SC's, ST's & OBC's

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